

Q&A to the state or national governments (of the OECD, EU, or G20 countries) that are interested in running the USL1 or USL0.x pilot studies

By USL Team (January 12th, 2015)
(Draft 1)

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TIME QA:

WHEN

Early part of this year between mid-February and May, but the earlier the better. As we'll basically take the first comes first service strategy. So if interested, please let us know at your earlier convenience.

HOW LONG IT WILL TAKE (for the entire operations)

This part depends on the levels we'll focus on. The entire operations, including the preparations and the meetings, etc., may take about 1 month, but the actual time the participating schools' students need will be most likely 1 week or 2 weeks.

HOW LONG will it take for the development stage before the actual PILOT STUDIES take place?

Probably we may need to arrive a few or several weeks before the actual online pilot study week starts to see all the textbooks and the levels of exams, to get the approvals of the materials we will cover from the teachers or DOE representatives and the levels of tests for the pilot study exams, to create tests, and to prepare the big scale online exams, etc.

WHY SHOULD YOU INVITE US AND RUN IT THIS SPRING instead of fall or next year?

Again, the USL1 is not just an education program. We try to create a major global movement. One of them is ending the extreme poverty, but the Millennium Development Goals of the UN end in 2015. The post-2015 will follow, but right now the policy makers are shaping all for the final version. Before the annual General Assembly of the UN in summer, we try to collect tens of thousands of student data worldwide to persuade the UN to create a new international treaty and the URF1 to rapidly transform our world.

PILOT STUDY TIME SCHEDULE FORMATS

SCENARIO 1

(Simple version that we used in the past. In the past we covered 1-2 month math materials in just 30-40 minutes)

- Monday: pilot test 1 & Survey 1 & some video interviews
- Wednesday: USL pilot lecture 1 & Survey 2
- Thursday: pilot test 2 & Survey 3 Friday: Results posted and the media coverages & interviews of many students.

SCENARIO 2

More elaborate version that we use for the first time to lower the skepticisms of the mass... may cover 2-3 weeks of math materials in 2 classes.

- Wednesday: pilot test 1 & Survey 1 & some video interviews
- Friday: USL pilot lecture 1 & Survey 2

- (Homework due next Monday)
- 2nd week Monday: pilot lecture 2 with a Homework due on Tuesday
- 2nd week Wednesday: 2nd pilot test & Survey 3.

Wednesday or Thursday or Friday: Results are published and the media coverages & interviews of many students.

So the second scenario 1.5 weeks for the actual operations.

SCENARIO 3

Or we may even do run two scenarios simultaneously depending on the districts of private vs. public.

WHO QA

HOW MANY STUDENTS ARE REQUIRED

In our last USL pilot studies in a town in Guatemala, we ran with 4 schools, about 800 students from the grades 2-11 basically in just 4-5 days (although the school strikes and policy changes pushed one or two to 1 or 2 weeks later, but it was a 5 day operation basically and all these were done face to face, not on internet.)

Since we will run all online pilot studies, we would like to have as many students as possible to be involved to get better statistical data. For each state or a small country, we expect at least 3,000-5,000 students (which may require about the participations from a few dozen schools.). Below 1,000 students as we have done that level in February 2014 for 800 students already.

WHICH GRADES WE WILL COVER

USL1 is primarily focusing on the primary school math. So we're thinking of the grades between 2-4 and 5-6 or 3-5. Something like that. If the support system for the primary school students are great, however, we may consider to run for the grade 7-9, but we'll do this only if the full scale participations of PISA or TIMMS or other authentic cross-country assessment organizations are involved.

WHY EXCLUSIVELY ONLINE PILOT STUDIES

There are many reasons why, but some of the main reasons are: the complete automations of the tests, surveys, video interviews, etc. can save a lot of time, papers, and efforts, and significantly reduce the costs of the operations.

Our rough plan for a week is roughly as follows:

SOME PREFERENCES WE HAVE

For the uniformity and ease of the operations, however, we prefer all public schools (although not required) because these are big scale operations and we prefer using the same textbooks at the same time to push the big scale operations. If we have a dozen of private schools, then there we have to over 30-40 textbooks and the preparation time may take much longer and we may not complete the whole projects within a month and instead may become 2 months.

ABSOLUTE MUST REQUIREMENTS

1. We have to have the experimental groups & the control groups. About 20-30% of the students may go to the control groups. As pilot studies, these will be necessary.
2. All the online tests should be examined and analyzed by at least two independent agents (preferably at least 3) from the UN or TIMMS or NAEP etc. primarily, not from people in your state or country governments because there can possibly be conflicts of interest and they may try to contaminate or distort the data, which have occurred throughout our previous USL pilot studies due to the fears of the school officials or teachers.
3. Also, the online exams and video streaming should be up to the international standard because we are trying to push the results to the national governments, UNESCO, and the UN as a whole. As long as the online operations are acceptable by the TIMMS or the UN, we can start running the pilots.
4. As many primary students may not be very online test savvy, the participating schools and governments should make sure that the pilot study participating students can handle online tests, home works, surveys, etc. because we cannot use the data for students who cannot respond properly online.

BUDGET & FUNDING QA

WHO WILL FUND?

The relevant governments (possibly the Department or Ministry Of Education), but as it is going to be all online, we don't think that the whole costs may be much. So the governments are basically expected to fund these quick pilot studies. (For private schools, the participating private schools should take care of their time and funds, but again due to the large number of students involved, if possible, we prefer focusing on the public schools so that we can use the same textbooks.

THE TOTAL COSTS

Aside from that, the corresponding governments have to pay for our transportations, housing, foods, etc., and basically payment for 1 month work with some payment arrangements as we are not authorized to your country (which we can discuss or negotiate privately as each state or country or city will be very different.)

FOR THE STATE LEVEL PILOT STUDIES

So, outside the 1 month payment for us, we suspect that the rest of cost for this may be less than 50,000 USD to 200,000 USD although there are many variables.

These are not going to be a million dollar projects. In most of the states in the U.S.A., for instance, we suspect that the entire operations may be possible for less than 200,000-300,000 USD.

FOR THE NATIONAL LEVEL PILOT STUDIES

For the national level, we'd like to run each pilot studies with at least 10,000 students per country. ... Almost at the levels of PISA or TIMMS. So the preparation times may take 1-2 months instead of 1 month and the operation costs may be 1-3 Million USD most likely although this is purely our guess.

PUBLICITY QA:

NEWS MEDIA COVERAGE GUARANTEES

STATE OR CITY LEVELS

For the city or state level USL1 pilot studies, the participating cities or state governments should

prearrange the significant media coverages immediately after the pilot study results come out. Even at the city or state levels, we will give preferences to the governments that will provide the maximum publicities immediately after the final results come out for a certain period of time.

NATIONAL LEVELS

For the national level USL1 pilot studies, we expect the significantly more UN involvements and all the major national news coverages of many major TV or news networks to maximize the impacts to the global awareness and to the UN. We will give the preferences to the governments that will provide the maximum national media publicities immediately after the final results come out for a certain period of time. The longer and the more, the better as we need the maximum exposures to create a global movement.

WHAT & WHY QA [BENEFITS]

THE BENEFITS (for your city, state, or country)

USL1 is not just one of breakthroughs in education. Its expected potential contributions to the economy - if the entire nation adopt it - will be far bigger than any other factor at least for the past over half a century. For more details, please visit our website www.uslgoglobal.com.

1) Economic reasons:

Let's try a national example. Our general rule of thumb - akin to the Moore's Law in computing power - the time it takes to double the GDP will roughly halve.

For instance, countries like U.S.A. or Canada with the current GDP growth rates of about 2.5% will take about 30 years to double the GDP. After USL1 reforms, this 30 years will be reduced roughly to 15 years. So if we assume that the nationwide USL1 reform takes place in 5 years - say 2020 - then in 2050, the GDPs of Canada or U.S.A. may have grown a bit over 2x larger than the current GDPs without USL1, but with the USL1 reforms, their GDPs will grow to about 4x larger than the current GDP of 2015, meaning the extra surplus GDP will be $4x - 2x \sim 2x$ surplus GDP!

Now, if we look at the surplus after about 60 years after the reform - as this will be a bit after the retirements of the currently 8-10 year old students - the surplus GDP will be 4x surplus GDP.

For the world average GDP growth rate, which is currently fluctuating around 3.5% annually, to double it will take slightly over 20 years. With USL1, it may take about 1 decade. So after 5 decades - half a century - with USL1 reforms, the world average GDP may be about 6x larger than the current world GDP. With the USL1 reform, the world average GDP growth would about 45x to 50x (64x

minus about 5 year reform time) larger than now. So the surplus GDP of the world average may be roughly at least 40x larger than the current world GDP in about 55 years from now.

2) To overcome all major global crises in 10-20 years (at least economically)

With 40x-50x of the surplus economy can resolve the top 5 hardest global crises about 10 times while the currently expected GDP growth of the world is totally stuck due to the overwhelming financings required to overcome these crises.

For more details, please visit our Back Of the Envelope Calculation Working Paper Series.

3) Uniqueness of USL1 (Nothing like this ever happened before.) Without USL1, boosting the national math skill average drastically have been attempted by all OECD member countries or other developed countries have rarely improved and if a few or several improved, they improved 1/3-1/4 of what USL1 can do in decades, not in 2-4 years.

4) USL1 is NOT going to be a corporation. It is going to be something that we call UGNSE1 (Unified Global Network of Social Enterprise) designed to build the eco-friendly circular economy based on the renewable energy. So the financial gains stay within the city, state, or country to support the local communities although a certain percent will be distributed to something that we try to establish via the UN called URF (Unified Redistribution Fund) which will focus on the most critical global crises as its potential fund size will be far bigger than any country, let alone the UN. This is possible because the USL1 will contribute to these colossal GDP surplus and everything else completely pales in comparison, especially as time goes on. So, your state and country is opening the first bold step to make this possible. The governments, various groups and NGOs that support the USL1 movement will get the first benefits of the USL1 official releases.

5) If the government is interested, during our pilot study developments, we'll start forming the blueprints of the board of trustees and members and will create the seed for the next steps as a token of gratitude for the USL1 pilot study supporting governments. We will try to partially form the tentative committees so that the next pilot studies - as there will be various versions of USL - can run smoothly and start forming our USL1 branch social enterprise together to empower not just by math education, but by boosting the economy, renewable energy, protecting environment, all at the same time. In the long run, for the USL1 participating governments, this may well be the most profound benefits the governments and the corresponding cities, states, or nation will receive.

6) The cost benefits and saving much time:

The governments that don't support USL1 pilots at the early stage will be queued to the end of the USL1 official releases and if they want to join the memberships, the costs will be substantially larger - say twice or thrice more - than those that supported USL1 by supporting the USL1 pilot studies. This is our way of returning our gratitude for those who have the innovative visions. For the governments that lack both the innovative visions and even lack the appreciation of the major innovations deserve less.

7) USL1 is just the beginning. When USL 2, 3, 5, 6 are released, all will be sequential. So only those that supported USL1 early will have the prioritized access to use **them**. Over the years and decades, these factors will make the staggering differences to the USL1 member states and countries.

8) We are soliciting to numerous countries. So if you'd like to start a bit late, we may no longer have the time slots for you. Since the potential gains are colossal, but the USL1 pilot study operation costs are not even half a million dollars in most cases and the actual pilot week will last just 1 week or so, it becomes simply will to run them or not instead of the budget shortages or other issues. So as the preparation time will last only a few weeks and later students have the final exams in May or June, we strongly recommend you to start conversations starting in January or February so that we can run the USL1 pilots in February, March, and April tightly.

There are many other reasons, but to confuse the readers less, we'll end here.

Having listed all the cons and pros of running our USL1 pilot studies together in 2015, please ask us any question if they arise and we hope that we can start a very ambitious and yet totally rational and peaceful revolution together to transform our world to a much better direction in a short period of time.

Thank you very much for your interest.

USL team

January 12th, 2015